

Selective DNA markers for *Apera spica-venti*

Version 0

Description

Creation, backup, storage and availability of the dataset of candidate selective DNA markers for *Apera spica-venti*

Funder

Latvian Council of Sciences

Grant

DNS marķieru izstrāde parastās rudzusmilgas (*Apera spica-venti*) sēklu noteikšanai augsnes sēklu bankā

Researchers

Anete Boroduske (orcid:0000-0003-0077-9811), Brandon Sinn (orcid:0000-0002-5596-6895), Elza Kaktiņa (orcid:0009-0008-5745-6160), Jevgenija Necajeva (orcid:0000-0002-0828-9721)

Organizations

Univeristy of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Selective DNA markers for Apera spica-venti](#)

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Creation, backup, storage and availability of the dataset of candidate selective DNA markers for *Apera spica-venti*

Researchers:

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[Jevgenija Necajeva \(orcid:0000-0002-0828-9721\)](#)

Organizations:

[Univeristy of Latvia](#)

Contact: [Jevgenija Necajeva](#)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Sciences](#)

Grants: [DNS marķieru izstrāde parastās rudzusmilgas \(*Apera spica-venti*\) sēklu noteikšanai augsnes sēklu bankā](#)

Project:

3. License

License:

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2024-10-10](#)

4. Templates

[Descriptions](#)

[Sequencing data](#)

To test the selected markers, DNA isolated from up to 300 individual *Apera spica-venti* plants and at least 20 other species that are most widespread in the region

will be used. A selection of samples will be used for Sanger sequencing of the amplified fragments.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

To test whether the markers are selective for the target species and non-selective for individual genotypes of the target species

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

others

FASTA

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

There are no relevant datasets

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

plant biologists, evolutionary biologists, weed scientists

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers - DOI)?

Yes

doi

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

Sample collection sites (georeferenced) and dates, species names.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

no licenced software is required.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

txt

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

Yes

Scientific names of the plants and standard place coordinates will be used.

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2025-12-31

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

The data will be available for an indefinite period of time

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Jevgenija Necajeva (orcid:0000-0002-0828-9721)

Collection of data, creation of metadata, and deposition

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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